

Finite Element Simulation of the 2D Lid-Driven Cavity Molten Salt Reactor Benchmark using FreeFEM

Ruggero Rosselli^{1,2,*}, Grégoire Allaire², Cyril Patricot¹, Maria Adela Puscas³, François Madiot¹, Nathan Greiner¹

¹Université Paris-Saclay, CEA, Service d'Études des Réacteurs et de Mathématiques Appliquées, 91191, Gif-sur-Yvette, France;

²Centre de Mathématiques Appliquées CMAP, CNRS UMR 7641, École Polytechnique, Institut Polytechnique de Paris, Route de Saclay, 91128 Palaiseau, France;

³Université Paris-Saclay, CEA, Service de Thermo-hydraulique et de Mécanique des Fluides, 91191, Gif-sur-Yvette, France

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.20803789

ABSTRACT

The multi-physics nature of Molten Salt Reactors (MSRs) requires the development of advanced simulation tools that accurately take into account the strong coupling between the different physics at play. Several coupling strategies between existing industrial codes have been implemented and are present in the literature. For research purposes however, such as testing new models and numerical methods, it can be convenient to use more flexible simulation platforms. One such platform is the finite elements code FreeFEM, which is used to implement a coupled stationary neutronics-thermal hydraulics model of MSR using the native Lagrange elements provided by FreeFEM. The 2D lid-driven cavity benchmark is calculated and the results compared to the solutions present in the literature. Qualitatively, the agreement between the different codes is excellent for all the benchmark steps. Some discrepancies are observed, mainly due to different modelling choices but also due to the different numerical schemes used. The maximum discrepancies on the outputs of interest are of the order of 2%, verifying the model developed in FreeFEM. Some improvements are nonetheless advised, including upwinding, using different types of elements and adaptative mesh refinement. Overall, FreeFEM proves to be a flexible and efficient platform to rapidly prototype and test reactor physics models.

Keywords: MSR, 2D lid-driven cavity, Finite Elements, FreeFEM, Multi-physics

1. INTRODUCTION

Molten Salt Reactors (MSRs) are a type of nuclear reactor where the nuclear fuel is dissolved in a molten salt, which also serves as the primary coolant by circulating in a so-called fuel circuit. For this reason, the neutronics and thermal-hydraulics of MSRs are strongly coupled, requiring advanced simulation tools to accurately model their behaviour. Many different codes and coupling strategies are presented in the literature. A few of them are summarized in [1], where they are compared on a benchmark case. For research purposes, however, it is often convenient to use more flexible platforms to rapidly prototype and test numerical reactor physics models and methods. One such platform is the finite element code FreeFEM, which can solve partial differential equations using weak formulations and arbitrary finite element spaces on arbitrary unstructured and adapted meshes [2]. In this work, a coupled neutronics-thermal hydraulics model of MSR core is implemented in FreeFEM using the native Lagrange elements provided. This model is developed to solve the 2D lid-driven cavity MSR ("CNRS") benchmark [1], which consists of several steps of increasing complexity, starting from steady-state single-physics problems up to fully-coupled transient multi-physics simulations. For this reason, and due to the nature of

*ruggero.rosselli@cea.fr

FreeFEM, the model is effectively divided into separate physics modules, which are then coupled together as needed. Section 2 describes consecutively the different steps of the benchmark together with the associated FreeFEM implementations. For each step, the results obtained are compared to those present in the literature in Section 3. Some conclusions and perspectives are finally drawn in Section 4.

2. BENCHMARK

The lid-driven cavity problem is well-known in fluid dynamics and serves as a benchmark for testing numerical methods. We consider a $2\text{ m} \times 2\text{ m}$ square cavity (whose domain we call Ω) filled with a fissile, Molten Salt Fast Reactor (MSFR)-like molten salt. The top lid is moved at a constant velocity $u_{\text{lid}} = 0.5\text{ m s}^{-1}$ while the other walls are kept stationary. The neutronics is solved using 6 energy groups. For brevity, the full details of the benchmark are omitted here, but can be found in [1].

2.1. Step 0.1

First, the incompressible Navier-Stokes equations are solved for the salt velocity u and pressure p . They can be written as:

$$\nabla \cdot \left(p\mathbb{1} - \mu \left(\nabla u + \nabla^T u \right) \right) + \rho(u \cdot \nabla)u = 0 \quad \text{in } \Omega \quad (1) \quad u = u_{\text{lid}} \quad \text{on the lid,} \quad (3)$$

$$-\nabla \cdot u = 0 \quad \text{in } \Omega \quad (2) \quad u = 0 \quad \text{on } \partial\Omega \setminus \text{lid} \quad (4)$$

where μ and ρ are the salt viscosity and density, respectively. The problem is implemented in FreeFEM using P2 spaces for the components of the velocity u and P1 for the pressure p , granting compatibility under the Ladyzhenskaya-Babuška-Brezzi (LBB) inf-sup condition. Since no Neumann boundary condition is specified, the pressure p is only determined up to a constant offset. Hence, we add a stabilisation term $+\varepsilon p$ to Equation (2), taking $\varepsilon = 10^{-10}$. Since this problem has a Reynolds number $\text{Re} = 40$, a laminar flow is expected. The problem is then initialised solving first a reduced Stokes problem (no velocity advection) to impose Equations (3) and (4). Then, using a Newton method, the linearised Navier-Stokes problem is solved iteratively until convergence.

2.2. Step 0.2

Secondly, the neutronics generalised eigenvalue problem is solved for the neutron flux ϕ and effective multiplication factor k_{eff} with static salt and uniform temperature. In this work, multi-group diffusion theory is used. Hence, the void boundary condition imposed on $\partial\Omega$ translates to a Robin boundary condition on the neutron flux [3]. We then have:

$$(\mathcal{L} - \mathcal{H})\phi = \frac{1}{k_{\text{eff}}}\mathcal{F}\phi \quad \text{in } \Omega, \quad (5) \quad J_g^- = \frac{1}{4}\phi_g + \frac{D^g}{2}\frac{\partial\phi_g}{\partial n} = 0 \quad \text{on } \partial\Omega, \quad (6)$$

where \mathcal{L} is the loss operator, \mathcal{H} the scattering operator, \mathcal{F} the fission operator, J_g^- the incoming neutron current for group g , D^g the diffusion coefficient for group g and $\partial \cdot / \partial n$ the normal derivative at the boundary $\partial\Omega$. The problem is solved using the EigenValue function available in FreeFEM (based on ARPACK) using P2 elements for the flux ϕ , introducing Equation (6) directly in the weak formulation.

2.3. Step 0.3

The velocity field u and power p_{fis} calculated in Steps 0.1 and 0.2, respectively, are now used to solve the heat transport problem for the temperature distribution T with adiabatic walls:

$$-\nabla \cdot (k\nabla T) + \rho c_p (u \cdot \nabla)T = p_{\text{fis}} - \gamma(T - T_{\text{ref}}) \quad \text{in } \Omega, \quad (7) \quad -k \partial T / \partial n = 0 \quad \text{on } \partial\Omega, \quad (8)$$

where k is the salt thermal conductivity, c_p its specific heat capacity, γ the heat exchange coefficient and T_{ref} the exchanger temperature. In FreeFEM, P2 elements were used for the temperature T .

2.4. Step 1.1

Next, the neutronics problem is solved taking into account the displacement of the Delayed Neutron Precursors (DNPs) due to the (fixed) salt velocity u calculated in Step 0.1. In FreeFEM, the same solver for Step 0.2 is adapted to include the explicit calculation of the diffusion-advection-decay equations for 8 DNP groups concentrations, again using P2 elements.

2.5. Step 1.2

The neutronics problem as described in Step 1.1 is now coupled to the temperature equation, effectively introducing a two-way coupling between neutronics and thermal-hydraulics, all while keeping the fixed velocity field u from Step 0.1. In FreeFEM, the solver from Step 1.1 is modified to include the temperature feedback directly in the cross sections and coupled iteratively to the temperature solver from Step 0.3.

2.6. Step 1.3

Then, buoyancy is taken into account in a simplified setting (no-slip boundary conditions on all walls, including the lid, i.e. $u_{\text{lid}}^{1,3} \equiv 0$). In FreeFEM, the velocity field u is then calculated solving the Navier-Stokes equations adding the buoyancy term $-g\alpha(T - T_{\text{ref}})$ in the momentum equation, where g is the gravitational acceleration and α the thermal expansion coefficient. The Navier-Stokes and temperature equations are solved together (monolithically), via Newton iterations until convergence as in Step 0.1. The calculated velocity and temperature are then given as input to the neutronics solver from Step 1.2, which is then used without modifications to calculate the flux and power distribution in the cavity. The calculated power distribution is then sent back to the thermal-hydraulics solver, iterating until convergence.

2.7. Step 1.4

In this final step, the complete, fully coupled, stationary problem is solved for varying lid velocities $u_{\text{lid}} \in [0.0, 0.1, 0.2, 0.3, 0.4, 0.5] \text{ m s}^{-1}$ and power levels $P_{\text{fis}} \in [0.2, 0.4, 0.6, 0.8, 1.0] \text{ GW}$. The same approach from Step 1.3 is used in FreeFEM, with minimal differences to take into account u_{lid} and P_{fis} .

3. RESULTS

Here we present the results obtained with FreeFEM obtained at each step of the benchmark, systematically comparing them to the results from the other participants. Since activities were carried out at CEA to develop a neutronics-thermo-hydraulics coupling between industrial codes APOLLO3 and TrioCFD dedicated to MSRs, their benchmark results are also included in the following [4]. The differences between these codes are expected to be more significant in the neutronics steps of the benchmark, while they should be negligible in the thermal-hydraulics steps. No particular mesh is prescribed for the benchmark, so the participants have all chosen different meshes. A uniform structured triangular 100×100 mesh is used for all steps, obtained by bisecting each cell of a 100×100 square grid (triangular elements are native to FreeFEM). The complete set of FreeFEM results can be found in [5].

3.1. Step 0.1

The solution of Equations (1) and (2) calculated by FreeFEM is shown in Figure 1. The solutions along the horizontal cut $y = 1 \text{ m}$ (AA') and the vertical cut $x = 1 \text{ m}$ (BB') are compared to the solutions calculated by the benchmark participants (including CEA's TrioCFD) and shown in Figures 2 and 3. Qualitatively, the agreement is excellent for all the four profiles and between all codes. The L2 discrepancies were also calculated and are reported in Table I. It is noted that the discrepancies are all around

Figure 1. Step 0.1: FreeFEM calculated velocity streamlines.

Figure 2. Step 0.1: horizontal velocity profile along AA'.

Figure 3. Step 0.1: vertical velocity profile along BB'.

1 %, with a maximum of 1.30 % for $u_y(BB')$. Although a finer meshing partially improves these discrepancies slightly, for simplicity the 100×100 mesh is retained for the following steps as it provides a good balance between accuracy and computational cost. Additionally, a second calculation was also performed using the convect FreeFEM operator, which introduces upwinding for the velocity advection. The difference with the previous Newton method solution is negligible, within 0.01 %, so it is not reported here for brevity. Several possible improvements can be considered for the current implementation: (i) different types of elements and solution schemes; (ii) adaptive meshing to have a non-uniform mesh, finer at the boundaries and near the bottom corners of the cavity; (iii) parallelisation via the PETSc library to introduce finer meshes.

Table I. Step 0.1: discrepancies (%) between FreeFEM and participants' codes on the velocity profiles.

Quantity	CNRS	PoliMi	PSI	TUD	TrioCFD
$u_x(AA')$	1.11	0.92	0.55	1.16	0.68
$u_y(AA')$	0.81	0.70	0.52	0.88	0.69
$u_x(BB')$	0.67	1.16	0.80	0.69	0.82
$u_y(BB')$	0.71	0.97	1.30	0.86	1.12

3.2. Step 0.2

The power distribution in the cavity calculated by FreeFEM is shown in Figure 4, while the comparison of the calculated fission rate profiles with other participants' codes is presented in Figure 5. Notably, PoliMi and PSI use diffusion solvers, while CNRS use simplified transport SP_N solvers and TUD use discrete ordinates S_N solvers. Three different CEA solvers were chosen for the comparison, namely a diffusion solver (CEA-diff), and higher order solvers (CEA- SP_3 and CEA- S_8). Qualitatively, the different codes are in excellent agreement on the calculated fission rate profiles. The discrepancies are reported in Table II. We note that FreeFEM has its smallest discrepancy of 0.11 % with CEA-diff, which is the most similar to the FreeFEM implementation. In general, the discrepancies are all below 1 %, with a maximum of 0.79 % for PoliMi. The calculated reactivities are also reported in Table III. We note that all codes calculate about 400 pcm of reactivity. In particular, those codes taking into account higher orders of anisotropy (in particular TUD- S_6 , CEA- SP_3 and CEA- S_8) calculate higher reactivities, of about 580 pcm. It is also noted that FreeFEM predicts the same value as CEA-diff (both diffusion solvers using the same mesh), with only a 0.1 pcm difference, which is encouraging and suggests a correct implementation of the problem in FreeFEM. The FreeFEM solver can be improved in several ways: (i)

Figure 4. Step 0.2: FreeFEM power distribution.

Figure 5. Step 0.2: fission rates.

using different types of elements, (ii) adopting alternative eigenvalue strategies (e.g. inverse or shift-and-invert Krylov methods instead of standard Arnoldi iterations), (iii) improving the linear algebra treatment of the multi-group system through suitable iterative solvers and preconditioning, and (iv) exploiting parallelisation via the SLEPc/PETSc libraries. As noted, more accurate transport solvers give better results, but would be an unnecessary complication for this study. The current implementation also suffers from relatively high computational costs due to the dimension of the multi-group problem matrices. This issue becomes particularly relevant when adding more variables (i.e. starting from Step 1.1).

Table II. Steps 0.2 – 1.3: discrepancies (%) between FreeFEM and other codes.

Step	Quantity	CNRS-SP ₁	CNRS-SP ₃	PoliMi	PSI	TUD-S ₂	TUD-S ₆	CEA-diff	CEA-SP ₃	CEA-S ₈
0.2	$R_{\text{fis}}(\text{AA}')$	0.49	0.24	0.79	0.49	0.72	0.16	0.11	0.21	0.20
0.3	$T(\text{AA}')$	0.11	0.10	0.15	0.09	0.15	0.14	0.18	0.22	0.22
	$T(\text{BB}')$	0.22	0.23	0.25	0.32	0.24	0.28	0.42	0.43	0.43
1.1	$\sum_i \lambda_i c_i(\text{AA}')$	0.63	0.76	0.54	0.68	0.66	0.73	1.01	1.08	1.09
	$\sum_i \lambda_i c_i(\text{BB}')$	1.19	1.25	1.10	1.08	0.94	1.06	1.46	1.51	1.51
1.2	$T(\text{AA}')$	0.15	0.14	0.12	0.08	0.16	0.14	0.16	0.20	0.20
	$T(\text{BB}')$	0.23	0.24	0.31	0.32	0.26	0.29	0.42	0.43	0.43
	$\Delta R_{\text{fis}} \Big _{0.2}^{1.2}(\text{AA}')$	1.47	1.13	1.73	3.47	2.40	2.38	1.08	1.46	1.40
	$\Delta R_{\text{fis}} \Big _{0.2}^{1.2}(\text{BB}')$	0.94	1.04	1.30	0.99	2.67	1.89	1.44	1.69	1.69
1.3	$T(\text{AA}')$	0.07	0.05	0.14	0.08	0.11	0.04	0.12	0.13	0.14
	$T(\text{BB}')$	0.08	0.05	0.16	0.06	0.16	0.10	0.14	0.16	0.16
	$u_x(\text{AA}')$	0.45	0.08	0.44	2.01	0.70	0.26	1.91	2.13	2.13
	$u_y(\text{AA}')$	0.44	0.15	0.26	0.62	0.63	0.18	1.17	1.18	1.18
	$u_y(\text{BB}')$	0.40	0.15	0.21	1.00	0.49	0.17	0.69	0.55	0.55
	$\sum_i \lambda_i c_i(\text{AA}')$	0.77	0.80	0.99	0.64	0.47	0.29	1.46	1.51	1.52
	$\sum_i \lambda_i c_i(\text{BB}')$	2.58	2.53	0.52	2.38	0.67	0.24	1.09	1.03	1.04

Table III. Steps 0.2 – 1.4: comparison of calculated reactivities (pcm).

Quantity	FF	CNRS- SP ₁	CNRS- SP ₃	PoliMi	PSI	TUD- S ₂	TUD- S ₆	CEA- diff	CEA- SP ₃	CEA- S ₈
$\rho^{0.2}$	465.9	411.3	353.7	421.2	411.7	482.6	578.1	466.0	584.5	583.6
$\Delta\rho _{0.2}^{1.1}$	-59.3	-62.5	-62.6	-62.0	-63.0	-62.0	-60.7	-62.7	-62.3	-62.3
$\Delta\rho _{1.1}^{1.2}$	-1144.5	-1152.0	-1152.7	-1161.0	-1154.8	-1145.2	-1122.0	-1141.6	-1119.5	-1120.6
$\Delta\rho _{0.2}^{1.3}$	-1205.0	-1220.5	-1220.7	-1227.0	-1219.6	-1208.5	-1184.4	-1206.2	-1183.8	-1185.0
$\Delta\rho _{0.2}^{1.4}$	-1190.2	-1204.8	-1205.2	-1214.0	-1199.8	-1193.0	-1169.7	-1191.4	-1169.6	-1170.6

3.3. Step 0.3

The temperature distribution calculated by FreeFEM is shown in Figure 6, while Figures 7 and 8 present the comparison of the calculated temperature profiles along the BB' cut. The AA' profiles are in excellent

Figure 6. Step 0.3: FreeFEM temperature distribution.

Figure 7. Step 0.3: temperature profile along BB'.

Figure 8. Step 0.3: zoom of Figure 7.

agreement, and are not shown here. From Figure 7 it is noted that FreeFEM predicts a lower temperature at the top of the cavity ($x = 1$ m, $y = 2$ m). This is likely due to the different numerical methods adopted. Figure 8 shows a zoom of the center of the cavity, where some small spatial fluctuations can be observed in the FreeFEM solution. These are likely due to the lack of upwinding in the advection term of the heat equation, which can lead to spurious oscillations in convection-dominated problems. The discrepancies between FreeFEM and other codes are reported in Table II. The discrepancies are all below 0.5%, but for all codes higher for the $T(\text{BB}')$ profiles, which is consistent with the observations above.

3.4. Step 1.1

Albeit part of a larger eigenvalue problem, the DNP balance equations are of the same type as the heat equation solved in Step 0.3 (diffusion-advection-decay). Hence, since the velocity field u is common, the DNP activity distribution is very similar to the temperature distribution in Figure 6. Indeed, it can be shown that the profiles of the total DNP activity along the AA' and BB' calculated by FreeFEM are in good agreement with the other codes, though again some numerical oscillations appear along BB' similarly to those observed for T in Step 0.3. Table II reports the discrepancies between FreeFEM and the other codes. These discrepancies are relatively higher with respect to the previous steps, and once again are higher for the vertical cut BB'. The maximum discrepancy is 1.51% for CEA-SP₃ and CEA-S₈

on the BB' profile. Overall, however, the discrepancies remain acceptable, especially considering the "second order" role of the DNPs in the global physics of the system. Table III reports the calculated reactivity differences $\Delta\rho|_{0.2}^{1.1} = \rho^{1.1} - \rho^{0.2}$ with respect to Step 0.2. The reactivity losses of around 60 pcm are expected and are due to the circulation of DNPs to less reactive zones of the core. It is shown that the FreeFEM calculation is in fair agreement with the other codes, although it undershoots the reactivity loss by about 3 pcm with respect to the other codes, which is probably due to the discrepancies on the DNP concentrations described above. While the FreeFEM implementation works, further verification is envisaged. Upwinding should be introduced to correct numerical oscillations. A different strategy to solve for the DNP groups concentrations could be sought, using different element types and mesh configurations.

3.5. Step 1.2

The temperature and fission rate change $\Delta R_{\text{fis}}|_{0.2}^{1.2} = R_{\text{fis}}^{1.2} - R_{\text{fis}}^{0.2}$ with respect to Step 0.2 are calculated with FreeFEM and the discrepancies with other codes along the cuts AA' and BB' are shown in Table II. While the discrepancies are very low for the temperature profiles, they can rise up to about 3% for the fission rate changes. This is likely due to the accumulation of the discrepancies already observed in Steps 0.3 and 1.1. The calculated reactivity differences $\Delta\rho|_{1.1}^{1.2}$ with respect to Step 1.1 are reported in Table III. The reactivity loss in this step is much higher than in Step 1.1 (about 1000 pcm vs about 60 pcm), due to the relative higher strength of thermal feedbacks with respect to the DNPs flow feedbacks. The FreeFEM calculation is in fair agreement with the other codes and is in particular close to the diffusion codes (PoliMi, PSI and CEA-diff). Overall, the implementation of the thermal feedback in FreeFEM appears to work well and is deemed satisfactory for the purposes of this benchmark.

3.6. Step 1.3

The velocity, temperature and precursors activities distributions are calculated with FreeFEM and compared to the other codes along the two cuts AA' and BB'. The discrepancies are reported in Table II. Here, we note that the calculated temperatures are in excellent agreement, with all discrepancies below 0.2%. The discrepancies on the velocity profiles are considerably higher than in Step 0.1, rising to about 2% for u_x (AA'). Similarly, the discrepancies on the total DNP activity profiles are also higher than in Step 1.1, rising to about 2.5%. This is likely due to the different schemes used for the solution of the coupled thermal-hydraulics problem and the different flow conditions in the cavity. The calculated reactivity differences $\Delta\rho|_{0.2}^{1.3}$ with respect to Step 0.2 are reported in Table III. The calculated reactivity losses are all in good agreement. In particular, we note that the FreeFEM result is again close to CEA-diff. The higher order transport codes (TUD-S₆ and CEA-S₈) again predict lower reactivity losses, of about -1185 pcm.

3.7. Step 1.4

For brevity, only the calculated reactivity for the case with $u_{\text{lid}} = 0.5 \text{ m s}^{-1}$ and $P_{\text{fis}} = 1 \text{ GW}$ is reported in Table III. The FreeFEM result is in good agreement with the other codes, and again close to CEA-diff, with a discrepancy of about 1 pcm. The discrepancies between FreeFEM and a selection of participants' codes on the reactivities calculated at all u_{lid} and P_{fis} are shown in Figures 9 to 11. In particular, Figure 9 shows that the discrepancy with CEA-diff increases for higher u_{lid} and lower P_{fis} . This is possibly due to the different treatments of the thermal-hydraulics. The discrepancies decrease again at higher P_{fis} , likely due to the dominance of the thermal effects over the flow effects. Figures 10 and 11 show the discrepancies with the finite elements TUD-S₂ and TUD-S₆ transport solvers, respectively. Figure 10 shows that the discrepancies with TUD-S₂ are flat at about 2 pcm, while those with TUD-S₆ increase rapidly for higher P_{fis} , independently of u_{lid} .

Figure 9. Step 1.4: reactivity discrepancies between FreeFEM and CEA-diff.

Figure 10. Step 1.4: reactivity discrepancies between FreeFEM and TUD-S₂.

Figure 11. Step 1.4: reactivity discrepancies between FreeFEM and TUD-S₆.

4. CONCLUSION

A multiphysics model of stationary neutronics - thermal hydraulics MSR was implemented in FreeFEM. The code was compared to other participants to the 2D lid driven cavity benchmark, showing overall good agreement on all the calculated profiles, with maximum discrepancies with other benchmark participants' codes of about 1% and a global maximum of about 3%. All the calculated reactivities are also in good agreement with other codes, considering the differences in the neutronics models used. Some discrepancies are nonetheless observed, mainly due to the treatment in FreeFEM of the advection terms in the thermal-hydraulics and DNP balance equations. These will be improved by introducing upwinding schemes in the current implementation. Due to the nature of the FreeFEM platform, the current implementation is specific to the case studied here and would require some modifications to the variational formulations to be adapted to other geometries and boundary conditions. However, the flexibility of FreeFEM allowed for a rapid development of the multiphysics model, which will serve as a base for the development of adjoint methods for the sensitivity analysis of MSRs in future works [6].

REFERENCES

- [1] M. Tiberga, R. G. G. de Oliveira, E. Cervi, J. A. Blanco, S. Lorenzi, M. Aufiero, D. Lathouwers, and P. Rubiolo. "Results from a multi-physics numerical benchmark for codes dedicated to molten salt fast reactors." *Annals of Nuclear Energy*, **volume 142**, p. 107428 (2020).
- [2] F. Hecht. "New development in FreeFem++." *Journal of Numerical Mathematics*, **volume 20**(3-4), p. 251–265 (2012). URL <https://freefem.org/>.
- [3] P. Reuss. *Neutron Physics*. Nuclear engineering. EDP Sciences (2008).
- [4] N. Greiner, F. Madiot, Y. Gorse, C. Patricot, and G. Campioni. "A New Calculation Strategy for Molten Salt Reactor Neutronic-Thermal-Hydraulic Analysis Implemented with APOLLO3® and TRUST/TrioCFD." *Nuclear Science and Engineering*, **volume 197**, pp. 3000–3021 (2023). URL <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/00295639.2023.2197043>.
- [5] R. Rosselli. "FreeFEM MSR 2D Lid Driven Cavity Benchmark." (2025). URL <https://doi.org/10.17632/c588cs6vps.1>.
- [6] R. Rosselli, G. Allaire, C. Patricot, M. Puscas, F. Madiot, and N. Greiner. "Adjoint Sensitivity Analysis of a 1D Stationary Neutronics-Thermohydraulics Coupled Molten Salt Reactor Model." pp. 1761–1770. American Nuclear Society. URL <https://www.ans.org/pubs/proceedings/article-58205/>.